
CSCCE Community of Practice new member onboarding survey

Introduction

BACKGROUND

The Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement (CSCCE) provides support and training for scientific community managers in a variety of ways including hosting a community of practice (CoP) for anyone interested in community-building in STEM. This survey forms part of our onboarding process to the CoP and is sent to all new members in a welcome email.

WHAT THIS SURVEY IS FOR

This survey is designed so that CSCCE staff can learn more about what you'd like to see in a CoP for scientific community managers. This will inform our programming and the creation of resources for the group. The survey also gives you an opportunity to let us know about anything you'd like to share with the CoP — as a speaker, curator, or in some other way.

USE OF DATA

The data collected will be reviewed by CSCCE staff to determine future programming for the CSCCE CoP for scientific community engagement managers.

If we report on the survey responses (e.g., in a blog post or webinar), all responses will be anonymized such that you will not be personally identifiable.

If you submit your email address, you consent to CSCCE staff contacting you about your responses and participation in the CSCCE CoP. We will not pass your email address on to anyone else.

About you

Please help us to get to know you.

1. Your name

2. Your job title

3. Your affiliation/name of your organization or community

4. Your email address

5. Add me to the CSCCE mailing list

<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes
<input type="checkbox"/>	No
<input type="checkbox"/>	I'm already on it!

Your interests

Please let us know about what you'd like from the community of practice.

6. Which topics would you like to discuss in a community of practice for scientific community managers? (Select all that apply.)

<input type="checkbox"/>	Community strategy
<input type="checkbox"/>	Community manager skill sets
<input type="checkbox"/>	Current research into community-building
<input type="checkbox"/>	Leadership development
<input type="checkbox"/>	Ambassador/advocacy programs
<input type="checkbox"/>	Community guidelines, codes of conduct and escalation policies
<input type="checkbox"/>	Metrics and evaluation
<input type="checkbox"/>	Diversity, equity and inclusion in community-building
<input type="checkbox"/>	Burnout, resilience, self-care and self-advocacy
<input type="checkbox"/>	Organizational culture change
<input type="checkbox"/>	Tools/technology selection
<input type="checkbox"/>	Tools/technology adoption
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)

7. In what ways would you prefer to participate in the CSCCE community of practice? (Select all that apply.)

<input type="checkbox"/>	Reading/downloading content from the Slack group
<input type="checkbox"/>	Participating in conversations in the Slack group
<input type="checkbox"/>	Attending the monthly community call
<input type="checkbox"/>	Presenting during the monthly community call
<input type="checkbox"/>	Reading a monthly newsletter summarizing the community's activities
<input type="checkbox"/>	Sharing data to enable creation of a community profile of your community
<input type="checkbox"/>	Participating in a book club or journal club
<input type="checkbox"/>	Leading a book club or journal club discussion
<input type="checkbox"/>	Joining a working group
<input type="checkbox"/>	Co-leading a working group
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)

8. Do you have resources or perspectives that you'd be willing to share with the community of practice? (Check all that apply.)

<input type="checkbox"/>	A report, book, manual or other item you've contributed to
<input type="checkbox"/>	Blog post(s) you've authored
<input type="checkbox"/>	Research that you've carried out
<input type="checkbox"/>	Interesting reading/links
<input type="checkbox"/>	Experiences of community management
<input type="checkbox"/>	Experiences about your career path
<input type="checkbox"/>	Not at this time, thanks
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)

9. Do you have any specific hopes for this community of practice? What would make it valuable for you? What would help you feel comfortable contributing to the group?

10. Do you have any concerns or things you'd like us to be particularly mindful of with this new community of practice?

11. Anything else that you'd like to share with us?

Citing and reusing this survey

CITATION AND REUSE

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